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III: Ideal Theory: Helpful Framework or Needless Abstraction?

The classic contractarians root much of their work in so-called “Ideal-Theory.” This standard of thought has, arguably, become the basis of our current society. The founding fathers of the United States read these works, our current political officials have likely read these works, and they have been continually taught and appraised in the many centuries since their publication. This ideal social contract theory has been, as many authors point out, used more as an ideology than simply as thought experiment intended to provide a hypothetical alternative to the world as it is. Rather than working off of a political framework that is based in reality, our systems of thought and governance have been based upon a fully imagined reality, a reality in which race, class, gender, and ability are non-issues – a reality in which all truly *are* equal. However, as is made clear by simply examining our social structures, all are not equal, at least not in material circumstances. This is not to say that we shouldn’t hold any lofty ideals – on the contrary, having an ideal is indeed necessary in order to take action within the world, but rather to say that we can no longer rely on the “old guard” of political liberalism, as it were. By examining and critiquing a few examples of the idealized model of social contract theory, I hope

to outline the discourse surrounding ideal theory, and to defend Charles Mills' "non-ideal theory."

From Hobbes to Rawls, "Ideal Theory" has shaped modern thought, and society as a whole. The modern Liberal tradition is based wholly upon this system of philosophy, and the Liberal tradition is what has largely informed the political decisions of the past few centuries, from the English Civil War to recent elections of presidents in the United States. Put simply, Ideal theory is a normative political theory that lays out a groundwork for an "ideal" model of a fully "just" government. As defined by a hesitant critic of ideal theory, Ingrid Robeyns,

The aim of ideal theory is to work out the principles of justice that should govern a society, that is, to propose and justify a set of principles of justice that should be met before we would consider a certain society just.⁴⁰

This is, most political philosophers would agree, the most basic definition and goal of ideal theory. By defining "justice" and by imagining the circumstances under which scattered individuals would come together to create a society and the structure at which they would logically arrive, the contractarians lay out a foundation on which to base governmental bodies, a framework from which to understand the political world. On the first impression, this seems a noble goal. After all, having frameworks, foundations, and ideals are all helpful and necessary in order to do anything. You can hardly bake a cake without using a recipe. However, Charles Mills, the main critic of ideal theory that I'll be focusing on, argues that ideal theory simply distracts from conversations and upholds dominant social hierarchies.

The so-called ideal theory more dominant in mainstream ethics is in crucial respects obfuscatory, and can indeed be thought of as in part ideological, in the pejorative sense of a set of group ideas that reflect, and contribute to perpetuating, illicit group privilege.⁴¹

⁴⁰ Ingrid Robeyns, "Ideal Theory in Theory and Practice," *Social Theory and Practice* 34, no. 3 (2008), 341–62, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23558712>, 343.

⁴¹ Charles W. Mills, "'Ideal Theory' as Ideology," *Hypatia* 20, no. 3 (2005), 165–84, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/3811121>, 166.

Mills believes that by focusing the conversation around ideal theory, the real conversations about justice and ethics are ignored, or placed in a secondary position. Mills instead argues for “non-ideal theory” to be the launching point for conversations of justice. Mills’ non-ideal theory is historical-materialist, meaning that it is rooted in the world as it is (not the world as it should be), and works from a grounded perspective to move forward. Looking at the history and current realities of oppression, we are better situated to solve the historical and current problems of oppression. Mills aims to make the case that ideal theory is really working as a mode of reproducing privilege, as a tool in the hands of white academics to justify their ignorance towards issues of race, class, gender, and many other identity factors. The way that Mills sees it, Ideal Contract Theory is being used as a descriptive philosophy rather than a normative one. Privileged groups are supposing that ideal contract theory is true, thus retaining their group privilege.

Contract theory, at the “state of nature” level, hasn’t always been blind to privilege, but privilege seems to always be slipped in nonetheless. Thomas Hobbes for example, in his *Leviathan*, allows for equality beyond ability, arguing that there is an equalizing force in nature.

Nature has made men so equal in the faculties of body and mind that, though there be found one man sometimes manifestly stronger in body or of quicker mind than another... the difference between man and man is not so considerable as that one man can claim to himself any benefit which another may not claim as well.⁴²

This formulation, allegedly true in the state of nature, is quickly manipulated by Hobbes into a hierarchical system in which the equality of mankind is negated – monarchy. Even from one of the earliest contract theorists, we see the basis of the theory being degraded in order to fit a privileged ideology. This previously “frictionless” state of nature devolves into a system that relies upon friction to operate, one that requires thinkers such as Hobbes to remain high in the

⁴² Thomas Hobbes, *The Essential Leviathan*, ed. Nancy A. Stanlick and Daniel P. Collette (Indianapolis, IN: Hackett Publishing Company, Inc., 2016).

order of things. As Mills points out, this frictionless ideal can never be achieved, and thus is unable to properly understand the world. “Since we're dealing with moral agents and not gasses, planes, or vacuum cleaners, the ideal in the ideal-as-idealized-model sense has here, of course, a crucial moral dimension along with the factual one.”⁴³ Beginning your argument with a frictionless, non-historical, fully equalized state of nature seems to be problematic, as it will then create models of society that have no real reflection in the world as it is.

There are a few misconceptions about ideal theory, as I see it. There are three dominant formulations of ideal theory that are easily distinguishable, and in order to understand Mills’ argument, we need to understand the differences between them. The first, most general understanding of ideal theory promotes idealism as a goal of promoting a perfect society. Of course, idealism isn’t necessarily bad! It is perfectly well and good to have ideals to live up to. Without a position to move towards, it’s impossible to move at all. Mills identifies this as the “ideal-as-normative” position, and recognizes that this is, of course, necessary. Mills’ issue comes in with the second, more “theoretical” understanding of ideal theory, which is ideal theory as a system of thought that supposes a frictionless plane to work with. This is the model that has been corrupted and used in order to distract from conversations regarding race. He calls this an “ideal-as-ideal theory.” Focusing the entire conversation around hypotheticals becomes problematic when all other conversations are halted in place. The third understanding is an ideal theory that Mills argues in favor of, an “ideal-as-descriptive theory” that identifies systems and hypothesizes the ideal working of said system while also recognizing the flaws that “prevent it from attaining ideality.”⁴⁴ This version of ideal theory identifies issues and provides opportunity for improvement, which plays hand in hand with non-ideal theory.

⁴³ Mills, “‘Ideal Theory’ as Ideology,” 167.

⁴⁴ Mills, “‘Ideal Theory’ as Ideology,” 167.

This brings us to a criticism of Mills. Erman and Möller argue that Mills misses the point with his dismissal of ideal theory, but I don't think that they fully grasped the three *kinds* of ideal theory laid out above. They use the example of Sweden's "Vision Zero" traffic initiative as an example of why ideal theory is good, and why it is better than non-ideal theory. "It is far from clear why an ideal vision zero principle, while requiring a lot of additional judgments in order to be applied, would be less motivating than a non-ideal principle that aimed at 300 killed annually."⁴⁵ This "Vision Zero" program has the intended purpose of reducing traffic deaths to zero, which is a noble goal. They argue that if Mills is completely dismissing ideal theory (which he isn't doing), then he dismisses initiatives such as this. Again, I don't think they understand the distinctions, so, using their own example, I will attempt to propose how each model (ideal-as-normative, ideal-as-ideal, and ideal-as-descriptive) would approach the question of traffic deaths.

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The "ideal-as-normative" framework would say, broadly, that we shouldn't have any traffic deaths. This is good. This is a normative statement that recognizes traffic deaths as being harmful to society. The "ideal-as-ideal" model would imagine a world in which traffic deaths don't occur. In this ideal world, no one dies as a result of traffic deaths. This is all well and good, but doesn't actually have much to say. We can hypothesize about a world in which no one dies in traffic accidents as much as we want, and fully flesh this world out, but in the end, it becomes very difficult to apply to the world as it is, the material circumstances of traffic deaths. Mills' "ideal-as-descriptive framework would do a similar thing to the "ideal-as-ideal" model,

⁴⁵ Erman, Eva, and Niklas Möller, "Three Failed Charges Against Ideal Theory," *Social Theory and Practice* 39, no. 1 (2013), 19–44, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/23558470>, 33.

but with a key difference: it would recognize that traffic deaths happen, and we need to work to ensure that they happen less by addressing the causes. We can imagine a world where traffic deaths do not occur, and then compare that model to the world-as-it-is, and understand where the discrepancy lies, which is exactly what Sweden's "Vision Zero" plan is working to do. By recognizing our own imperfections as an integral part of the theory, as essential to the conversation at hand, we can move forward with an ideal in mind and a plan in place to move closer to that ideal.

Of course, the bulk of Mills' writing isn't focused on Hobbes' ideal theory or traffic laws, but rather on a more modern author, John Rawls. Rawls has been the main authority on ideal theory, and political philosophy as a whole, for the past 50 odd years. His seminal work, *A Theory Of Justice*, has informed most subsequent works on political philosophy, and truly sparked the debate regarding ideal vs non-ideal theory. One of the most famous thought experiments that Rawls uses throughout his work is the "veil of ignorance," which, in a rudimentary summary, assumes that if any given person were stripped of all of their identity factors and placed in charge of creating an ideal society they would naturally shape a society that is egalitarian, not knowing what position they would hold in said society. Obviously, this model is not meant as a true identity-less future, but as a hypothetical. Mills' complaint from earlier stands true once again: there is a crucial moral dimension involved in focusing on the hypothetical model rather than a model that can be actualized. Identity, whether we like it or not, isn't something that can be easily stripped away, even hypothetically. By flattening identity onto a plane that can be removed, Rawls arguably devalues race and gender, upholding what Mills defines as the "Racial Contract," and what Carole Pateman terms the "Sexual Contract," respectively. Supposing that race and gender are non-issues can only be done from the

perspective of a white man who has never had his identity denied or devalued by the dominant power structures.

This intentional ignorance of diversity and oppression is heavily prevalent in Rawls' work. Discussions on race, gender, or other factors that contribute to the oppression of people in the world as it is are rare, and when these identity factors are discussed, they are discussed in order to dismiss them. From Rawls himself, discussing the work that he did in *A Theory of Justice*,

The serious problems arising from existing discrimination and distinctions based on gender and race are not on its agenda, which is to present certain principles of justice and then to check them against only a few of the classical problems of political justice as these would be settled within ideal theory.⁴⁶

Rawls's argument here is that he has no need to focus on race and gender, that choosing "only a few" problems is a sufficient method of formulating justice. In the next paragraph, Rawls places the burden of theorizing about race onto the shoulders of anyone willing to take it. It may be argued that Rawls does provide a framework from which to work, but Mills' critique holds that there is, again, an important distinction between allowing for conversation about oppression and actually having a meaningful conversation about oppression.

There are those that argue that by creating a theory that abstains from participating in the discussion of oppression, Rawls really is making an intentional choice to disown oppression, essentially solving the problem by eliminating any difference. "But why should Rawls be accused of ignoring oppression rather than considering oppression in the sense that it has to be removed in order for a basic structure of a society to qualify as just?"⁴⁷ Tommie Shelby is another of those that believes Rawls can be used to face issues of oppression. Although Rawls

⁴⁶ John Rawls, *Justice as Fairness: A Restatement*, ed. Erin Kelly (Cambridge, MA: Belknap Press of Harvard University Press, 2001), 66.

⁴⁷ Erman, Eva, and Niklas Möller, "Three Failed Charges Against Ideal Theory," 42.

only briefly discusses race outright, that doesn't mean that his theories can't be extended to

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address race, Shelby argues. “What he does say can still aid those of us who do focus our theoretical energies on questions of racial justice.”⁴⁸ A lack of concrete consideration, I would respond to both, is not solving the issue. Mills, again, has a response. “Why should anyone think that abstaining from theorizing about oppression and its consequences is the best way to bring about an end to oppression? Isn't this, on the face of it, just completely implausible?”⁴⁹ Further, the fact that Rawls' main comments regarding oppression only serve to shift the

burden of the discussion onto another's shoulders proves how deeply rooted oppression is to ideal theory. The largest figure in modern contractarianism, a white professor, has so little to say about oppression that he decides it's best for someone else to do the dirty work of non-ideal theory.

In defense of ideal theory, it is indeed somewhat helpful to have fully abstracted understandings of the world. Seeing beyond the reality in which we live isn't an easy task, and normative models of justice are necessary. Having this purely theoretical framework does provide some insight into the way the world *should* be.

Moral theory such as a theory of justice contains more than the slogan that summarizes its conclusion. ... Rawls's theory of justice may provide us with guidance concerning which of two states is more fair.⁵⁰

⁴⁸ Tommie Shelby, "Race and Ethnicity, Race and Social Justice: Rawlsian Considerations," *Fordham Law Review* 72, 1697-1714, (New York, NY), 1698.

⁴⁹ Mills, "'Ideal Theory' as Ideology," 171.

⁵⁰ Erman, Eva, and Niklas Möller, "Three Failed Charges Against Ideal Theory," 30.

The comparison of two states is a decent example of this. All states, all cultures, will have their own codified systems of justice and fairness, but leaving that all behind and comparing these systems against a purely abstracted system does create a launching point for future improvement.

As James Boettcher argues,

Rawlsian ideals are not needlessly utopian. Instead, they are meant to facilitate the analysis of other legitimate moral-political problems, namely, economic inequality and, in the case of political liberalism, religious disagreement and conflict.⁵¹

This facilitation, I will concede, is much harder to do using non-ideal theory. It is true that the “frictionless plane” model does allow more space for theorizing about morality and political ideals. But, to stay true to Mills, I continue to wonder if this abstraction is the best solution.

In the modern usage of ideal theory, we seem to have forgotten that it is just a theory. Philosophers and politicians seem to have embraced the abstract as reality, and used it to excuse any injustices that may occur. “Abstractions of ideal theory are not innocent ... they can be seen in the U.S. context in particular as exacerbated philosophical versions of apologist concepts long hegemonic in the self-image of the nation.”⁵² Our country has been founded on ideal theory, straight from Locke. “All men are created equal.” While this statement may be true – no human is *inherently* better than another – this single sentence works to excuse and ignore circumstance, privilege, and hardship. We may

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be all *created* equal, but by no means are we *born* equal. We must recognize this non-ideal world and respond as such. “The best way to bring about the ideal is by recognizing the non-ideal, and that by assuming the ideal or the near-ideal, one is only guaranteeing the perpetuation of the

⁵¹ James Boettcher, “Race, Ideology, and Ideal Theory,” *Metaphilosophy* 40, no. 2 (2009), 237–59, <http://www.jstor.org/stable/24439662>,

⁵² Mills, “‘Ideal Theory’ as Ideology,” 181.

non-ideal.”⁵³ Placing emphasis on the ideal, we forget to reflect upon reality, we strategically ignore the inequality of the world as it is. For this reason, Mills argues, and I agree, ideal theory makes the goal that we are reaching for – creating a just and fair world – almost impossible.

To take Mills’ non-ideal theory one step further, I want to argue that not only do we need to root ourselves in the world as it is, the “ideal-as-descriptive,” but that we need to further define what this “non-ideal ideal” would look like. In order to do so, we need to embrace some of the arguments upheld by the more traditional contractarians, namely, the idea that the ideal form of government would result from all subjects, all people, consenting to the rule of law and willingly submitting to some larger body-politic. Formulating a system that is “just” and that is palatable to all is no easy task, but a necessary one nonetheless. The first step required in this process would be to take Mills’ position: Ideal theory has led us astray and distracted the field of philosophy from actually acting in the world. This is the same basic case used by Marx in his dismissal of the Hegelians, and resulted in a historical-materialist ideology, one that arguably recognizes non-ideal theory as the true root of thought. We are striving to describe what is and what should be, not what could be in a hypothetical. This shift of thought is not a quick process, and should not be rushed. In allowing non-ideal theory to be the dominant way of thought in political philosophy, those in power must come to terms with the inequalities that our world still faces, and those without power will be better able to understand the roots of oppression. Overturning the current political philosophy of our age isn’t fully necessary – all that is required is a reformulation, a reimagining of the way in which philosophy interacts with the world.

⁵³ Mills, “‘Ideal Theory’ as Ideology,” 182.